

Split domination of splitted graphs

A.Esakkimuthu ^{1*}, O. Nethaji ²^{1,2}PG and Research Department of Mathematics,
Kamaraj College, Thoothukudi-628 003 Tamilnadu, India.ORCID iD: [0000-0001-6251-040X](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6251-040X)ORCID iD: [0000-0002-2004-3521](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2004-3521)

Received: 07 Jul 2021

•

Accepted: 01 Dec 2021

•

Published Online: 30 Dec 2021

Abstract: In this paper, we introduce and investigate some new splitted graphs called $S(P_l), S(H_l), S(P_l^+), S(P_l \circ NK_1)$. Also we discuss some splitted graphs and it's properties are obtained.

Key words: Domination, split domination number and splitted graph

1. Introduction

The concepts of graph theory instead of [7]. By a graph, we mean a finite simple and undirected graph. The vertex set and edge set of a graph G denoted are by $V(G)$ and $E(G)$ respectively. Let G be a graph. For each vertex v of a graph G , take a new vertex u . Join u to those vertices of G adjacent to v . The graph thus obtained is called the splitting graph of G . It is denoted by $S(G)$. For a graph G , the splitting graph S of G is obtained by adding a new vertex v corresponding to each vertex u of G such that $N(u) = N(v)$ and it is denoted by $S(G)$. The notions of splitting graphs were studied and investigated of many more authors for Example [1], [11], [12], [13], [14] and [15]. A dominating set D of a graph $S(G)$ is said to be a split dominating set of $S(G)$ if the subgraph induced by $V - D$ is disconnected. The minimum cardinality among all split dominating sets is called the split domination number of $S(G)$ and is denoted as $\gamma_s[S(G)]$. In this paper deal some splitted graphs namely $S(P_l), S(H_l), S(P_l^+), S(P_l \circ NK_1)$.

2. Preliminaries

[10] A set D of vertices in a splitted graph $S(G) = (V, E)$ is called a dominating set if every vertex in $V - D$ is adjacent to some vertex in D . [9] A dominating set D of a graph $S(G)$ is said to be a split dominating set of $S(G)$ if the subgraph induced by $V - D$ is disconnected. The minimum cardinality among all split dominating sets is called the split domination number of $S(G)$ and is denoted as $\gamma_s[S(G)]$. Esakkimuthu [4, 5] was introduced and studied the idea of path related graphs and connected domination graphs. The Recently, the idea of the Domination and independent domination graphs are studied by several researchers for Example [2], [3], [6], [8], [9], [10] and [16] so on.

3. γ_s -Main Results

Theorem 3.1. $\gamma_s S(P_l) = \lceil l/2 \rceil$ when $l \equiv 1(mod 2)$.

©Asia Matematika, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5840065](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5840065)

*Correspondence: esakkimsu005@yahoo.com

Proof. Let $V[S(P_l)] = \{c_h, d_h : 1 \leq h \leq l\}$.

Let $E[S(P_l)] = \{(c_h c_{h+1}) \cup (d_h c_{h+1}) \cup (c_h d_{h+1}); 1 \leq h \leq l-1\}$. In P_l , vertex c_{h+1} is adjacent to $c_{h+1}, d_{h+2}, c_h, d_h$ where as c_{h+2} is adjacent to $c_{h+3}, d_{h+3}, c_{h+1}, d_{h+1}$.

By definition c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} are adjacent and in every fourth of c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} the center vertices satisfy the γ_s -ing set condition and c_{i-1} is adjacent to $c_{i-2}, c_{i-2}, c_i, d_i$.

Hence, $\gamma_s[S(P_1)] = \lceil l/2 \rceil$.

For example, $\gamma_s[S(P_3)] = \{c_2, c_3\} = 2$ as seen from the following fig-1. □

Figure 1. $S(P_3)$.

Theorem 3.2. $\gamma_s S(P_l) = 2^{\lceil l/4 \rceil}$ when $l \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$

Proof. Let $V[S(P_l)] = \{c_h, d_h : 1 \leq h \leq l\}$.

Let $E[S(P_l)] = \{(c_h c_{h+1}) \cup (d_h c_{h+1}) \cup (c_h d_{h+1}); 1 \leq h \leq l-1\}$.

In P_l , vertex c_{h+1} is adjacent to $c_{h+1}, d_{h+2}, c_h, d_h$ where as c_{h+2} is adjacent to $c_{h+3}, d_{h+3}, c_{h+1}, d_{h+1}$.

By definition c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} are adjacent and in every fourth of c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} the center vertices satisfy the γ -ing set condition and c_{i-1} is adjacent to $c_{i-2}, c_{i-2}, c_i, d_i$.

Hence, $\gamma_s[S(P_1)] = 2^{\lceil l/4 \rceil}$ For example, $\gamma_s[S(P_4)] = \{c_2, c_3\} = 2$ as seen from the following fig-2. □

Theorem 3.3.

$$\gamma_s S(H_l) = \begin{cases} l+1 & \text{if } l \equiv 1 \pmod{4} \\ 2 & \text{if } l = 3. \end{cases}$$

Proof. Case I. Let $V[S(H_l)] = \{c_h, d_h, c'_h, d'_h : 1 \leq h \leq l\}$. Let $E[S(H_l)] = \{(c_h c_{h+1}) \cup (d_h c_{h+1}) \cup (c_h d_{h+1}) \cup (c_{h+1/2} c'_{h+1/2}) \cup (c_{h+1/2} d'_{h+1/2}) \cup (d_{h+1/2} c'_{h+1/2}) \cup (c'_h c'_{h+1}) \cup (c'_h d'_{h+1}) \cup (d'_h d'_{h+1}); 1 \leq h \leq l-1\}$.

For $1 \leq h \leq l+1/2$. In H_l vertex c_{h+1} is adjacent to $c_{h+1}, d_{h+2}, c_h, d_h$ where as c_{h+2} is adjacent to $c_{h+3}, d_{h+3}, c_{h+1}, d_{h+1}$ by definition c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} are adjacent and in every fourth of c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} the center vertices satisfy the γ_s -ing set condition.

Figure 2. $S(P_4)$

The vertex $c_{l+1/2}$ and $c'_{l+1/2}$ Split dominating any other vertex in the graph from the remaining vertex.

Consider, for $(l + 3)/2 \leq h \leq l$, vertex c_{h+1} is adjacent to $c_{h+1}, d_{h+2}, c_h, d_h$ where as c_{h+2} is adjacent to $c_{h+3}, d_{h+3}, c_{h+1}, d_{h+1}$ by definition c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} are adjacent and in every fourth of c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} the center vertices satisfy the γ_s -ing set condition, and c_{l-1} is adjacent to $c_{l-2}, d_{l-2}, c_l, d_l$. The same process applicable for the set of vertex c'_{h+1} and c'_{h+2} .

Case II. When $l = 3$, Let $V[S(H_l)] = \{c_h, d_h, c'_h, d'_h : 1 \leq h \leq l\}$, Let $E[S(H_l)] = \{(c_h c_{h+1}) \cup (d_h c_{h+1}) \cup (c_h d_{h+1}) \cup (c_{h+1/2} c'_{h+1/2}) \cup (c_{h+1/2} d'_{h+1/2}) \cup (d_{h+1/2} c'_{h+1/2}) \cup (c'_h c'_{h+1}) \cup (c'_h d'_{h+1}) \cup (d'_h d'_{h+1}); 1 \leq h \leq l - 1\}$. In H_l , The vertex $c_{l+1/2}$ and $c'_{l+1/2}$ γ_s -ing set condition. \square

For example, $\gamma_s[S(H_5)] = \{c_2, c_3, c_4, c'_2, c'_3, c'_4\} = 6$ and $\gamma_s[S(H_3)] = \{c_2, c'_2\} = 2$ as seen from the following fig-3.

Figure 3. $S(H_3)$ and $S(H_5)$

Theorem 3.4.

$$\gamma_s S(H_l) = \begin{cases} l + 1 & \text{if } l \equiv 7 \pmod{8} \\ l - 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Proof. Case I. When $l \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$, Let $V[S(H_l)] = \{c_h, d_h, c'_h, d'_h : 1 \leq h \leq l\}$, Let $E[S(H_l)] = \{(c_h c_{h+1}) \cup (d_h c_{h+1}) \cup (c_h d_{h+1}) \cup (c_{h+1/2} c'_{h+1/2}) \cup (c_{h+1/2} d'_{h+1/2}) \cup (d_{h+1/2} c'_{h+1/2}) \cup (c'_h c'_{h+1}) \cup (c'_h d'_{h+1}) \cup (d'_h d'_{h+1}); 1 \leq h \leq l - 1\}$. For $1 \leq h \leq l + 1/2$, In H_l , vertex c_{h+1} is adjacent to $c_{h+1}, d_{h+2}, c_h, d_h$ where as c_{h+2} is adjacent to $c_{h+3}, d_{h+3}, c_{h+1}, d_{h+1}$ by definition c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} are adjacent and in every fourth of c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} the center vertices satisfy the γ -ing set condition, The vertex $c_{l+1/2}$ and $c'_{l+1/2}$ Split dominating any other vertex in the graph from the remaining vertex. Consider, for $(l + 3)/2 \leq h \leq l$, vertex c_{h+1} is adjacent to $c_{h+1}, d_{h+2}, c_h, d_h$ where as c_{h+2} is adjacent to $ch + 3, d_{h+3}, c_{h+1}, d_{h+1}$ by definition c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} are adjacent and in every fourth of c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} the center vertices satisfy the γ -ing set condition, and c_{l-1} is adjacent to $c_{l-2}, d_{l-2}, c_l, d_l$. The same process applicable for the set of vertex c'_{h+1} and c'_{h+2} .

Case II. Let $V[S(H_l)] = \{c_h, d_h, c'_h, d'_h : 1 \leq h \leq l\}$. Let $E[S(H_l)] = \{(c_h c_{h+1}) \cup (d_h c_{h+1}) \cup (c_h d_{h+1}) \cup (c_{h+1/2} c'_{h+1/2}) \cup (c_{h+1/2} d'_{h+1/2}) \cup (d_{h+1/2} c'_{h+1/2}) \cup (c'_h c'_{h+1}) \cup (c'_h d'_{h+1}) \cup (d'_h d'_{h+1}); 1 \leq h \leq l - 1\}$. For $1 \leq h \leq l + 1/2$. In H_l , vertex c_{h+1} is adjacent to $c_{h+1}, d_{h+2}, c_h, d_h$ where as c_{h+2} is adjacent to $c_{h+3}, d_{h+3}, c_{h+1}, d_{h+1}$ by definition c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} are adjacent and in every fourth of c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} the center vertices satisfy the γ_s -ing set condition, The vertex $c_{l+1/2}$ and $c'_{l+1/2}$ Split dominating any other vertex in the graph from the remaining vertex. Consider, for $(l + 3)/2 \leq h \leq l$, vertex c_{h+1} is adjacent to $c_{h+1}, d_{h+2}, c_h, d_h$ where as c_{h+2} is adjacent to $ch + 3, d_{h+3}, c_{h+1}, d_{h+1}$ by definition c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} are adjacent and in every fourth of c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} the center vertices satisfy the γ -ing set condition, and c_{l-1} is adjacent to $c_{l-2}, d_{l-2}, c_l, d_l$. The same process applicable for the set of vertex c'_{h+1} and c'_{h+2} . Hence $\gamma_s S(H_l) = l + 1$ if $l \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$ and $l - 1$ otherwise. For example, $\gamma_s[S(H_{11})] = \{c_2, c_3, c_6, c_9, c_{10}, c'_2, c'_3, c'_6, c'_9, c'_{10}\} = 10$ and $\gamma_s[S(H_7)] = \{c_2, c_3, c_6, d_6, c'_2, c'_3, c'_6, d'_6\} = 8$ as seen from the following fig-4. □

Figure 4. $S(H_7)$ and $S(H_{11})$.

Theorem 3.5. $\gamma_s S(H_l) = l$ when $l \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$

Proof. Let $V[S(H_l)] = \{c_h, d_h, c'_h, d'_h : 1 \leq h \leq l\}$, Let $E[S(H_l)] = \{(c_h c_{h+1}) \cup (d_h c_{h+1}) \cup (c_h d_{h+1}) \cup (c_h/2 c'_{(h/2)+1}) \cup (c_h/2 d'_{(h/2)+1}) \cup (d_h/2 c'_{(h/2)+1}) \cup (c'_h c'_{h+1}) \cup (c'_h d'_{h+1}) \cup (d'_h d'_{h+1}); 1 \leq h \leq l-1\}$. In H_l , vertex c_{h+1} is adjacent to $c_{h+1}, d_{h+2}, c_h, d_h$ where as c_{h+2} is adjacent to $c_{h+3}, d_{h+3}, c_{h+1}, d_{h+1}$ by definition c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} are adjacent and in every fourth of c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} the center vertices satisfy the γ_s - ing set condition, The same process applicable for the set of vertex c'_{h+1} and c'_{h+2} . Hence, $\gamma_s S(H_l) = l$ when $l \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$. For example, $\gamma_s[S(H_4)] = \{c_2, c_3, c'_2, c'_3\} = 4$ as seen from the following fig-5.

□

Figure 5. $S(H_4)$.

Theorem 3.6.

$$\gamma_s S(H_l) = \begin{cases} l + 2 & \text{if } l \equiv 6 \pmod{8} \\ l & \text{if } l \equiv 2 \pmod{8} \end{cases}$$

Proof. Case I. $l \equiv 6 \pmod{8}$, Let $V[S(H_l)] = \{c_h, d_h, c'_h, d'_h : 1 \leq h \leq l\}$, Let $E[S(H_l)] = \{(c_h c_{h+1}) \cup (d_h c_{h+1}) \cup (c_h d_{h+1}) \cup (c_h/2 c'_{(h/2)+1}) \cup (c_h/2 d'_{(h/2)+1}) \cup (d_h/2 c'_{(h/2)+1}) \cup (c'_h c'_{h+1}) \cup (c'_h d'_{h+1}) \cup (d'_h d'_{h+1}); 1 \leq h \leq l-1\}$. In H_l , vertex c_{h+1} is adjacent to $c_{h+1}, d_{h+2}, c_h, d_h$ where as c_{h+2} is adjacent to $c_{h+3}, d_{h+3}, c_{h+1}, d_{h+1}$ by definition c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} are adjacent and in every fourth of c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} the center vertices satisfy the γ_s - ing set condition, The same process applicable for the set of vertex c'_{h+1} and c'_{h+2} . Hence, $\gamma_s S(H_l) = l + 2$ when $l \equiv 6 \pmod{8}$.

Case II. $l \equiv 2 \pmod{8}$, Let $V[S(H_l)] = \{c_h, d_h, c'_h, d'_h : 1 \leq h \leq l\}$, Let $E[S(H_l)] = \{(c_h c_{h+1}) \cup (d_h c_{h+1}) \cup (c_h d_{h+1}) \cup (c_h/2 c'_{(h/2)+1}) \cup (c_h/2 d'_{(h/2)+1}) \cup (d_h/2 c'_{(h/2)+1}) \cup (c'_h c'_{h+1}) \cup (c'_h d'_{h+1}) \cup (d'_h d'_{h+1}); 1 \leq h \leq l-1\}$. The vertex $c_{l/2}$ and $c'_{l/2}$ Split dominating set any other vertex in the graph from the remaining vertex. For $1 \leq h \leq l/2$, In H_l , vertex c_{h+1} is adjacent to $c_{h+1}, d_{h+2}, c_h, d_h$ where as c_{h+2} is adjacent to $c_{h+3}, d_{h+3}, c_{h+1}, d_{h+1}$ by definition c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} are adjacent and in every fourth of c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} the center vertices satisfy the

γ_s - ing set condition, Consider, for $l/2 \leq h \leq l$ vertex c_{h+1} is adjacent to $c_{h+1}, d_{h+2}, c_h, d_h$ where as c_{h+2} is adjacent to $c_{h+3}, d_{h+3}, c_{h+1}, d_{h+1}$ by definition c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} are adjacent and in every fourth of c_{h+1} and c_{h+2} the center vertices satisfy the γ_s - ing set condition, The same process applicable for the set of vertex c'_{h+1} and c'_{h+2} . Hence, $\gamma_s S(H_l) = l$ example, $\gamma_s[S(H_{10})] = \{c_2, c_5, c_8, c_9, d_2, c'_2, c'_5, c'_8, c'_9, d'_2\} = 10$ and $\gamma_s[S(H_6)] = \{c_2, c_5, d_2, d_5, c'_2, c'_5, d'_2, d'_5\} = 8$ as seen from the following fig-6.

□

Figure 6. $S(H_6)$ and $S(H_{10})$.

Theorem 3.7. $\gamma_s S(P_l^+) = l$

Proof. Let $V[S(P_l^+)] = \{c_h, d_h, c'_h, d'_h : 1 \leq h \leq l\}$.

Let $E[S(P_l^+)] = \{(c_h c_{h+1}) : 1 \leq h \leq l\} \cup \{(c_h c'_h) \cup (c_h d'_h) : 1 \leq h \leq l\} \cup \{(d_h c_{h-1}) \cup (d_h c'_h) \cup (d_h c_{h+1}) : 2 \leq h \leq l-1\} \cup \{(d_1 c'_1) \cup (d_1 c_2) \cup (d_1 c'_1) \cup (d_1 c_{l-1})\}$. In P_l^+ , For $n \geq 2$, vertex c_h is adjacent to c_{h+1}, d_{h+1} for all $1 \leq h \leq l-1$ where as c_h is adjacent to c'_h, d'_h for all $1 \leq h \leq l$ and vertex c_{h+1} is adjacent to c_h, d_h for all $1 \leq h \leq l$ by defn c_h and c_{h+1} are adjacent and in every c_h and c_{h+1} $1 \leq h \leq l-1$ vertices satisfy the γ_s - ing set condition. Hence $\gamma_s S(P_l^+) = l$ example, $\gamma_s S(P_5^+) = \{c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5\}$ as seen from the following fig-7.

□

Theorem 3.8. $\gamma_s[S(P_l o N K_1)] = l$

Proof. Let $V[S(P_l o N K_1)] = \{c_h, d_h, c_{hg}, d_{hg} : 1 \leq h \leq l, 1 \leq g \leq N\}$.

Let $E[S(P_l o N K_1)] = \{(c_h c_{h+1}) : 1 \leq h \leq l-1\} \cup \{(c_h c_{hg} \cup (d_h c_{hg}) \cup (c_h d_{hg}) : 1 \leq h \leq l, 1 \leq g \leq N\} \cup \{(d_h c_{h-1}) \cup (d_h c_{h+1}) : 2 \leq h \leq l-1\} \cup \{(d_1 c_2) \cup (d_1 c_{l-1})\}$.

In $S(P_l o N K_1)$, Vertex c_h is adjacent to c_{hg}, d_{hg} for all $1 \leq h \leq l, 1 \leq g \leq N$, where as c_h is adjacent to $c_{h-1}, d_{h-1}, c_{h+1}, d_{h+1}$ for all $2 \leq h \leq l-1$.

Hence $\gamma_s[S(P_l o N K_1)] = l$ example, $\gamma_s[S(P_4 o N K_1)] = \{c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4\} = 4$, as seen from the following fig 8.

□

Figure 7. $S(P_5^+)$.

Figure 8. $S(P_4 \circ NK_1)$

Theorem 3.9. *Let G be a path splitted graph. Let k be maximum degree. Then $G - k$ is γ_s -ing set.*

Proof. Let G be a path splitted graph. Let k be maximum degree. Now, a cut vertices k of path splitted graph G , k is a point whose removal increases the number of components. So $G - k$ is disconnected graph. Then $G - k$ is γ_s -ing set. □

Acknowledgment

Split dominating sets of splitted graphs are useful for the communication and modeling network graphs

References

[1] Allan.R.B. and Laskar.R.C , On domination and independent dommination numbers of a graphs, Discrete math, 23 (1978) 73-76.

- [2] Chelvam T.T., Chellathurai S.R., A note on split domination number of a graph, *Journal of Discrete Mathematical Sciences and Cryptography* 12(2) (2009), 179-186.
- [3] Cockayne.C.J, Dawes.R.B. and Hedetniemi, Total domination in graphs, *Networks*, 10 (1980) 211-219.
- [4] Esakkimuthu.A, Near Mean Labeling of Path Related Splitted Graphs, *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology*, April 2018,vol 6, issue IV, Pp: 2252- 2258.
- [5] Esakkimuthu.A, Connected Domination Of Splitted Graphs, *International Research Journal Of Modernization In Engineering Technology And Science*, September 2021, Volume:03,Issue:09, Pp: 707 - 711.
- [6] Flach.P. and Volkmann.L, Estimations for the domination number of a graph, *Discrete math.*, 80 (1990) 145-151.
- [7] Harray.F, *Graph Theory*, Adadison-Wesley Publishing Company Inc,USA, 1969.
- [8] Hedetniemi.S.T. and Laskar.R.C, Connected domination in graphs, InB.Bollobas, editor, *Graph Theory and Combinatorics*, Academic Press, London(1984) 209-218.
- [9] Kulli V.R., Janakiram B., The split domination number of a graph. *Graph theory notes*, New York,XXXII,Pp : 16 -19, (1997).
- [10] Kulli V.R., Janakiram B., The minimal dominating graph. *Graph theory notes*, New York,XXVIII, Pp : 12 -15, (1995).
- [11] NellaiMurugan.A, Esakkimuthu.A, Independent Domination of Splitted Graphs, *International Journal of Mathematical Trends and Technology*, April 2014, Vol 8, Issu1,Pp: 56-63.
- [12] NellaiMurugan.A, Esakkimuthu.A, Edge Domination of Splitted Graphs, *International Journal of Modern Sciences and Engineering Technology*, 2014, Vol 1, Issu1,Pp: 23-29.
- [13] NellaiMurugan.A, Esakkimuthu.A, Domination and Total Domination of Splitted Graphs, *International Journal of Mathematical Archive*, April 2014, Vol 5, Issu 4, Pp: 118-126.
- [14] NellaiMurugan.A, Esakkimuthu.A, Domination of Complement of a Splitted Graphs, *Indian Journal of Applied Research*, April 2014, Vol 4, Issu4,Pp: 392-394.
- [15] NellaiMurugan.A, Esakkimuthu.A, Connected Double Geodetic Domination Number and Strong Split Double Geodetic Domination Number of a Graph, *International Journal of Advance Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering*, January 2016,vol 6, issu 1, Pp: 693 - 698.
- [16] Walikar.H.B, Acharya.B.D. and Sampathkumar.E, Recent developmentin the theory of domination in graphs, In *MRI Lecture Notes in Math. MahtaResearchInstit.*, Allahabad No.1, (1979).